

Abelian Group on the Binomial Coefficients of Combinatorial Geometric Series

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Abstract: This paper discusses an abelian group, also called a commutative group, under addition of the binomial coefficients of combinatorial geometric series. The coefficient for each term in combinatorial geometric series refers to a binomial coefficient. This idea can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

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1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to develop the multiple summations of geometric series, a new idea was stimulated his mind to create a combinatorial geometric series [1-11]. The combinatorial geometric series is a geometric series whose coefficient of each term of the geometric series denotes the binomial coefficient V_n^r . In this article, binomial identities and multinomial theorem is provided using the binomial coefficients for combinatorial geometric series.

2. Combinatorial Geometric Series

The combinatorial geometric series [1-11] is derived from the multiple summations of geometric series. The coefficient of each term in the combinatorial refers to the binomial coefficient V_n^r .

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \quad \& \quad V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3) \cdots (n+r-1)(n+r)}{r!},$$

where $n \geq 0, r \geq 1$ and $n, r \in N = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Here, $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ refers to the combinatorial geometric series and

V_n^r is the binomial coefficient for combinatorial geometric series.

$$V_0^1 = 1; V_1^1 = 2; V_2^1 = 3; V_3^1 = 4; V_4^1 = 5; V_5^1 = 6; \dots$$

$N = \{V_0^1, V_1^1, V_2^1, V_3^1, V_4^1, V_4^1, \dots\}$ is a set of natural numbers.

$W = \{0, V_0^1, V_1^1, V_2^1, V_3^1, V_4^1, V_4^1, \dots\}$ is a set of whole numbers.

$Z = \{\dots, -V_2^1, -V_1^1, -V_0^1, 0, V_0^1, V_1^1, V_2^1, \dots\}$ is a set of integers.

In general, a binomial coefficient is an integer such that $V_n^r \in N$.

Note that $V_0^r + V_1^r + V_2^r + V_3^r + \dots + V_{n-1}^r + V_n^r = V_n^{r+1} \Rightarrow V_{n-1}^{r+1} + V_n^r = V_n^{r+1}$,
 where $V_n^r = V_0^{r-1} + V_1^{r-1} + V_2^{r-1} + \dots + V_{n-1}^{r-1}$ and $V_0^r + V_1^r + V_2^r + \dots + V_{n-1}^r = V_{n-1}^{r+1}$.

Proof for $V_0^r + V_1^r + V_2^r + V_3^r + \dots + V_{n-1}^r + V_n^r = V_n^{r+1}$.

$V_0^r + V_1^r + V_2^r + V_3^r + \dots + V_{n-1}^r + V_n^r = V_n^{r+1} \Rightarrow V_{n-1}^{r+1} + V_n^r = V_n^{r+1}$.

Note that $V_n^r = \frac{(n+r)!}{n!r!}$.

$$V_n^r + V_{n-1}^{r+1} = \frac{(n+r)!}{n!r!} + \frac{(n-1+r+1)!}{(n-1)!(r+1)!} = (n+r)! \left(\frac{r+1}{n!(r+1)!} + \frac{n}{n!(r+1)!} \right).$$

$$V_n^r + V_{n-1}^{r+1} = (n+r)! \left(\frac{n+r+1}{n!(r+1)!} \right) = \frac{(n+r+1)!}{n!(n+r)!} = V_n^{r+1}.$$

$$\therefore V_n^r + V_{n-1}^{r+1} = V_n^{r+1}.$$

Hence, it is proved.

Also, $V_n^r = V_n^{r-1} + V_{n-1}^{r-1}$, which is the sum of partitions of V_n^r .

3. Abelian Group

$Z = \{-V_r^n, 0, V_r^n \mid n \geq 1, r \geq 0 \text{ \& } n, r \in N\}$ is a set of integers.

Closure property: Addition of any two binomial coefficients is also a binomial coefficient.

$(V_m^n + V_p^q) \in Z$ for all $V_m^n, V_p^q \in Z$.

Associativity: For all $V_m^n, V_p^q, V_r^s \in Z$, $V_m^n + (V_p^q + V_r^s) = (V_m^n + V_p^q) + V_r^s$.

Identity element: $0 + V_r^n = V_r^n + 0 = V_r^n$, where 0 is an identity element.

Inverse element: $V_r^n + (-V_r^n) = (-V_r^n) + V_r^n = 0$, where $-V_r^n$ is an additive inverse.

Commutativity: $V_m^n + V_p^q = V_p^q + V_m^n$ for $V_m^n, V_p^q \in Z$.

$(Z, +)$ is an abelian group under addition.

4. Conclusion

In this article, an abelian group was formed on the binomial coefficients of combinatorial geometric series under addition. This new idea can enable the scientific researchers for research and development further.

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